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Erasmus

The concept of multidisciplinary in the system of helping professions in the context of undergraduate education of a social worker and a special pedagogue.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The multiple problems of the 21st century have complexity in common and none of them can be addressed from the individual disciplines, but are transdisciplinary challenges (Max-Neef, 2005), trying to overcome the fragmentation of knowledge, beyond the enrichment of disciplines with different knowledge and the epistemological exchange and scientific methods of knowledge.

First of all, it should be made clear that multidisciplinary refers to the coordinated interaction of different areas of knowledge. This can be understood as a combination of a set of specialized knowledge that allows to address certain ideas and similar explorations among the classified knowledge, without abandoning or mixing the methodologies of each discipline. In other words, multidisciplinary conceives a series of paths related to an established paradigm and that walk linked in search of new discoveries. Therefore, in order to carry out this type of interaction, it is necessary to know how to work as a team, that is to say, to cooperate and collaborate for a common goal. (Márquez, 2016).

In the educational field, interdisciplinarity has served as a basis, from the epistemological point of view, for different curriculum integration proposals.

The inter-subject or interdisciplinary relationship is that which establishes the formation of the systems of knowledge, habits and skills that serve as the basis for all significant social qualities, in other words, this knowledge, habits and skills of the different subjects are integrated into systems that must necessarily be coordinated in such a way as to form in the student a generalized system of knowledge integrated into his or her conception of the world.

Alvarez (1999), states that the concept of inter-subject relationship encompasses not only the links that can be established between the knowledge systems of one and another, but also those links that can be created between the modes of action, ways of thinking, qualities, values, and points of view that enhance the different subjects.

In principle, the term interdisciplinary is applied in the pedagogical field to the type of scientific work that methodologically requires the collaboration of various disciplines and in general the collaboration of specialists from various traditional areas.

Interdisciplinarity involves researchers, practitioners, students and teachers with the aim of linking and integrating many schools of thought, professions or technologies, even with their specific perspectives, in pursuit of a common goal.

Today, multidisciplinary is key for all students to achieve their maximum development and for their own benefit. (Díaz, 2019).

2. PROFESIONALS RESOURCES

To achieve the total development of the students as individuals is the main objective of the teachers, as well as to benefit each one of the students and make them achieve the objectives and personal goals they set for themselves. However, although it may seem a very complicated challenge, with the collaboration and cooperation of professionals such as psychologists, school counselors, social workers or special pedagogues, students will achieve their goals and develop correctly and in their totality.

2.1. SPECIAL PEDAGOGES

Undoubtedly, Special Education in schools has been gaining more and more importance, since Special Education is an opportunity to advance on the road to equality for students.

Nowadays, the future of education lies in an inclusive education in which everyone (professionals, teachers, families, students, etc.) plays a particularly active role. From the teacher's point of view, we must consider the enormous challenge of building a school that is capable of organizing itself on the basis of integration and where difference is seen as something that enriches us and, therefore, makes us better in the eyes of society. (Moll, 2013).

In addition, the LOE, the Organic Law of Education in Spain 2/2006, May 3, in Chapter I, Article 71, entitled Students with specific educational support needs:

1. The educational administrations will provide the necessary means for all students to achieve the maximum personal, intellectual, social and emotional development, as well as the objectives established in general in this Law.

2. It is the responsibility of the educational administrations to ensure the necessary resources so that students who require educational attention different from the ordinary one, due to special educational needs, specific learning difficulties, high intellectual abilities, late entry into the educational system, or due to personal conditions or school history, may achieve the maximum possible development of their personal abilities and, in any case, the objectives established in general for all students.

And we can highlight one of those resources, which is the figure of the Special Pedagogue or PT.

The Special Pedagogue or Pedagogical Therapist (PT) is a teacher specialized in Special Education and who works as a teacher in Early Childhood, Primary and Secondary Education centers. And develops functions such as:

1. Attend and support students with Special Educational Needs.
2. Elaborate together with the teachers or professors the didactic material adapted for students with Special Educational Needs.
3. Elaborate together with the teachers or professors the Individualized Curricular Adaptations.
4. Coordinate periodically with teachers or professors in each area, as well as tutors.
5. Interview families of students with needs.

In short, the pedagogue is in charge of planning, organizing and managing the educational needs of each of the children in the school. He/she makes personalized plans and is a link between the specific educational needs, the families and the class group.

For this reason, and although it is mostly known only to the families of the students who need their services, special pedagogues are very important as a link in the educational community (teachers, students and families). They ensure that pupils do not fail and achieve their maximum development as pupils and as people.

2.2. SCHOOL COUNSELLOR

Guidance is proposed as a qualitative dimension of educational practice whose overall goal is the integral formation of the individual, enabling him/her to lead a balanced and prosperous future life (Dirección General de Renovación Pedagógica, 1990). Accordingly, guidance work is a quality intervention for the holistic and future-oriented training of pupils. This comprehensive training is the objective of guidance, both for curricular action (through the activities of the different subjects) and tutorial action (developing specific activities) and it is specified in three goals (Dirección General de Renovación Pedagógica, 1992; Luque, 1995):

1. To enable students to learn and study in an effective and autonomous way, to develop a certain reasoning ability, to build a positive academic self-concept and to give them the opportunity to internalise the use of appropriate learning strategies (school or academic guidance).
2. To enable students to make decisions concerning their future with as much information and advice as possible (vocational/career guidance).
3. To enable students to fulfil themselves as individuals and to integrate actively and successfully into society (personal guidance).

The responsibilities of the school counsellor in relation to the school's curriculum project are twofold. On the one hand, as an additional teacher in the school, responsible for a department which may involve most of the teaching staff. On the other hand, as a specialist in a position to advise the management team and the teaching staff on the decisions to be taken in relation to the school's curriculum project.

1. As one of the school's teachers: has the right and obligation to participate in the preparation of the school's curriculum project and annual plan. He/she is responsible for coordinating the elaboration and development of his/her guidance department's programming, which is integrated into the curricular project and the annual plan as a guidance plan.
2. As a specialist in psycho-pedagogical counselling: the function of the counsellor is to advise the management team and the teaching staff in the development of the school curriculum project and its implementation in the school's annual plan. This counselling involves two different tasks. On the one hand, to dynamise the collective work of

drawing up these documents and, on the other hand, to technically inform the decisions to be adopted in both, particularly those related to the treatment of diversity and those which may influence the development of the activities of the guidance department (Murillo and Riart, 1994; Antolín, Prieto and Moreno, 1995).

The functions of the counsellor in relation to the organisation of the school may be: to evaluate the climate and functioning of the organisation by means of questionnaires, interviews, mailboxes or other procedures, to identify dissatisfactions or problems and to suggest measures aimed at correcting organisational problems, mediating in possible conflicts. Organisational decisions embodied in the school's curricular project are relevant when it comes to responding flexibly to the needs of students and their diversity (González Franco, 1994; Puig, 1994; Tiradó, 1996; Agelet, Bassedas and Comadevall, 1997; Continente, Gol, Guijarro and Pinar, 1997).

The counsellor is responsible for advising teachers in their reflections on objectives, content, instruments and assessment criteria. Therefore, he/she may attend and participate in assessment sessions adopting different roles: as a spectator, to be informed of relevant data for other activities; as an advocate for students; as a moderator of conflicts and negotiator of compromises; or as an advisor on the best procedure to inform students and their families of the assessment results (Zabala, 1996).

The counsellor in the secondary school is not a teacher like any other, nor a specialist outside the educational tasks of the teaching team. He/she advises from the difference of functions, but from the equality of status; equality that is expressed in the attitude of those who join the centre with the attitude of learning as much as of contributing their experience and knowledge to the service of the common educational objectives.

In short, the educational counsellor is important because he/she is the one who helps children to improve their academic results. He/she gives equal opportunities to all pupils. It is very necessary to reduce the gap between people and to help them to improve and reduce school drop-out.

2.3. SOCIAL WORKERS

The educational environment is one of the many areas in which the Social Worker can carry out his or her functions. Educational centres are an ideal place for the early detection of social problems which, if detected and intervened in time, prevent the

development of more complex problems that lead students to a situation of risk of social exclusion. Despite the important role that the Social Worker plays in this field, not all the circumstances that surround him/her favour the execution of an adequate practice.

According to “Subdirección General de Educación Especial”, the social worker within the school environment is the professional who, in accordance with the educational project of the centre, collaborates with other professionals in favouring the integral development of the pupils, providing elements of knowledge of the pupils and the environment in the family and social aspects and intervening in these areas when necessary.

The functions of the Social Worker according to Dolores Fernández (n.d.) are the inclusivity of pupils in school, the family-school relationship, coexistence and social climate in schools, risk in childhood: the detection of risk situations in schools, truancy, parent training and co-knowledge, information and use of resources.

The interventions of social workers do not only focus on problems that pupils may have, such as absenteeism and educational failure, but also address conflictive social situations. The work they carry out aims to promote, provide and organise complementary training activities for specific groups of the population: integration of immigrants and disadvantaged groups, addictions, people with disabilities, youth, obesity, unemployment, anorexia, climate of coexistence, school bullying as a form of violence, detection of mistreatment and sexual abuse, among other sectors.

Another of the functions carried out by the Social Work professional in the field of education is research. The study of educational and social problems makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of intervention practice and, in turn, to propose efficient alternatives to reduce the negative social impacts on the Education System and improve the functioning of educational institutions. Its presence in scientific studies, regardless of the thematic area in which the professional is involved, enhances the understanding of the socio-educational reality and improves the design of future educational plans.

We can conclude, therefore, that the contributions and efficacy that Social Work offers to the Spanish Educational System are evidence of an important work of intervention in the face of the challenge of detecting the needs of the times. Its capacity to adapt its intervention to current problems, as well as its ability to have first-hand knowledge of

the situation of families and people in conflict situations, represent a combination of qualities that accentuate an effective intervention and reinforcement in the mediation and resolution of multiple problematic situations within the educational sphere.

3. INTERDISCIPLINARY COOPERATION

Interdisciplinary collaboration is a term widely used to describe any process in which individuals representing multiple viewpoints and role responsibilities work together towards goals that cannot be achieved individually. Collaboration between professionals goes beyond friendship and collegiality, it involves a real and consistent exchange of expertise and work that results in lasting professional relationships and the achievement of professional goals.

Teamwork and collaboration are necessary because meaningful solutions cannot be arrived at any other way. The training of teachers, social workers, and other human service professionals occurs in academic disciplines that each look at an issue or problem from their own particular angle. Collaboration is therefore a means of resisting this fragmentation and forming an integrated, collective view of the people and communities we serve.

The importance of school administration in fostering professional collaboration is paramount in all schools. By exhibiting the three professionals described above (special pedagogues, schools counsellors and social workers), principals can lead their schools toward more collective decision making and greater individual investment in school-wide initiatives and programs.

The respect and positive attitude towards other workers from different organizations is the basic component for effective cooperating relation. For establishing team cooperation is crucial that other members accept individual differences, learn to understand, respect others, and build personal relationships with other members of the teams. Every member is important and can bring something unique to the team. The multidisciplinary practice is unique even in the challenges which are involved. The cooperation of people from various fields brings differences for example in values, language, the ways of dealing with problems, strategies, and diverse elements of

professional behavior. The barriers to effective cooperation are mainly in the field of trust, responsibility, communication, and fight for power. (Stárek, 2021)

Therefore, with the individual work of each of the school professionals and the cooperation and collaboration between them, the objectives set by the educational community are achieved, with a common goal, the complete and total development of each pupil, guiding them and providing them with a path towards their professional and personal future.

4. CONCLUSION

Interdisciplinary collaboration in schools can provide a pathway to pupil success, thanks to the help and cooperation of great professionals, such as special pedagogues, school counsellors and social workers.

Despite their differences, especial pedagogues, school counsellors and social workers seem to share the idea that they operate in flawed bureaucracies that serve populations with growing needs. Specifically, in the field of education, they share a common goal, the success and full development of the learner.

Therefore, without the individual and team work of each of these educational professionals, the main aim and objective shared by all professionals in the educational community, including teachers, specialists, management team, students' families, and even the students themselves, would not be possible to achieve or successfully address.

So, we cannot forget these professionals, as they are essential in the educational community, helping teachers and students to achieve their maximum development and making each student the best version of themselves, and helping and guiding them to achieve their goals.

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